

Accumulation of Heavy Metals in Crops Surrounding Valsad City: A Baseline Study

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ABSTRACT: Toxic substances pose severe risks to living beings. The rise in industrial activities and anthropogenic actions has led to significant contamination of soil, air, and water. This contamination occurs chiefly by Pesticides used in agriculture and Heavy Metals from the Industries. The Present research focus on accumulation of heavy metals in soil, water and common crops grown in and around Valsad region of Gujarat, India. The study aims to investigate and evaluate levels of metals, *viz.* Cu, Zn, Pb, Co, Ni, Cd, and Hg. Approximately 15-20 crop samples including vegetables and fruits, 17 soil samples and 04 water samples were collected from different sites in winter and summer season from December 2022 to May 2023. Analysis was conducted on ICP-OES instrument in laboratory, revealed Cu and Co metal in soil samples, Cu and Hg in crops samples were on far side of permissible limit, while water samples were within the permissible limits. The order of concentration of metals in Crops were $Pb < Co < Cd < Hg < Zn < Ni < Cu$ creating need of calculation of Bioaccumulating Factor (BAF) indicating accumulation of metals in crops. Kakadkuva and Gundlav region showed high BAF value creating health risk for human as well as in animals.

KEYWORDS: *Accumulation, Toxic substance, Heavy metal, Crops, Valsad.*

INTRODUCTION:

We in general, often neglect our health and the quality of the food we consume. The fast and busy life and incorporation of manmade pollution, leads to the decline in the quality of soil, water and plants. Heavy metals also leach into the soil from the different sources, including urban, industrial aerosols resulting from fuel combustion, metal smelting, and other industrial activities (Bhatia et al, 2015). Additional sources of soil contamination include excessive pesticide use, micronutrient fertilizers, and manures such as sewage sludge (Bhatia et al, 2015). Therefore, it is requisite to find out toxic elements in crops grown by farmers in agricultural lands. A great number of researchers have worked on the accumulation of heavy metals in soil, water and plants. Scientists from India and abroad have examined

soil, water and plant samples from industrial and adjacent areas and reported diverse degrees of heavy metals contamination. These heavy metals were polluting aquatic resources and lives as well as agricultural and other plants/crops which ultimately becomes a part of food chain, causing harm to humans and animals (Patel & Das, 2015). Industrialization is often seen as sign of development, it can have detrimental effects on nature and the environment due to improper waste management by industries, such as those producing hazardous chemical or synthetic dyes. Rivers and their tributaries are particularly affected by these toxins leading to reduced soil fertility and crop quality. Hence, it is crucial to survey and analyses the quality of water, soil and crops at micronutrient level. Our research focuses on Valsad city region of Gujarat, and cover surrounding villages. Valsad have higher number of industrial areas with Paper, Chemical and Dyeing Industries established over the years, therefore detailed assessment and analysis of Soil, Water and Crops in these areas was thought imperative.

SITE SELECTION:

Valsad district spread in 2947 square kilometre area. In this, 50-55 square km area surrounding the Valsad city was chosen which also includes Industrial area.

SELECTED SITES:

Villages located at distances of minimum 10-12 km and maximum 50-55 km away from Valsad city and area near Gundlav GIDC are shown in fig.1

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Collection of Water Samples:

Water samples which farmers used as irrigation from different selected sites have been taken in thoroughly washed and dried plastic bottles and sent to the laboratory for further analysis. Village names and source of water samples are mentioned in table 1.

Collection of Soil Sample:

Surface soil samples weighing approximately 50 to 60gms were collected from a depth of 0-15cms (Bhatia et al, 2015; Meena et al, 2018) and They were air dried. Individually dried samples were manually crushed using mortar and pestle and passed through 2mm mesh size sieve (Sharma et al, 2008), mixed properly and stored in clean zip lock bags with labels and sent to the laboratory for further analysis. Selected sites for the soil samples are mentioned in table 2.

Collection of Crops/Plants:

Collected Plant Samples weighing approximately 250-500gms have been taken from different sites, through hand plucking. Inedible parts were removed from these samples (Sharma et al, 2008). Half of the samples were cut into small pieces and sun dried directly, labelled as unwashed samples while the rest of the samples were washed thoroughly with lukewarm water then cut and sun dried, labelled as washed samples. All the samples were dried till they became crisp so that they could easily be ground to fine powder. The grinding process was done using stainless steel mixer grinder and stored in air tight polythene bags with proper tags and sent to Konark Research Foundation Laboratory for further analysis. Selected sites and crop names from the different sites are mentioned in the table 3.

Solution making for heavy metal determination:

In order to prepare them for the extraction, digestion of the samples is mandatory. For wet digestion, in closed microwave digester, we took an accurately weighted maximum 0.5gm dry sample (soil and

cro) individual in Teflon material vessel. TFM was then introduced into safety shield. 7ml 65% purified conc. HNO_3 and 1 ml 30% purified H_2O_2 were added, to remove any residue from inner wall of the TFM, acid was added drop by drop and the sample was homogenized, the vessel was closed, introduced into rotor segment. The segment was inserted into microwave cavity, maintaining the 200°C temperature. Cooling the rotor was by air and by water until the solution reached room temperature. Then transferred the solution to a marked flask. Digested solution was diluted with reagent grade water up to 50ml; this was considered as test solution. Analysis of sample was done by inductive coupled plasma optical emission spectrometer (ICP-OES). For all the samples, blank results were taken and three different sets of concentration were used to calibrate the instrument. (Food safety and standards authority of India ministry of health and family welfare government of India New Delhi 2016)

Bio Accumulation Factor:

Bio Concentration Factor is the ability to transfer of metal from soil to the plant (Sonu et al, 2019). All plants require soil and water to grow, nourish and to complete their life cycle. These requirements can be fulfilled by absorbing water and minerals from the soil. These minerals may or may not store in some portions of plants. These minerals can also be in the form of heavy metals. By calculating the BAF (Bio Accumulating Factor), one can find out if a plant has accumulated heavy metals in major quantity and whether its consumption for the human and animal is harmful or not. If BAF is <1 or $=1$, it can indicate that the plant has absorbed heavy metals from the soil but these have not been accumulated and hence it is safe for human consumption. However, if BAF is >1 , it indicates that heavy metals have been accumulated in plant making it unfit and harmful for human as well as animal consumption (Bhatti et al, 2016).

Formula for BAF:

C_p/C_s

Where, C_p = concentration metal in plant and C_s = concentration metal in soil

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Results of Water Samples:

Water samples were collected from the selected sites *viz.* Saronda and Anklas (Umargao district), Kakdkuva (Dharampur District), Jespor (Valsad District) for the analysis of metal *Viz* Lead, Copper, Cadmium, Cobalt, Nickel, Zinc and Mercury. Out of all seven metals only Copper and Zinc were detected between the range of 0.001 - 0.021mg/kg and 0.003- 0.007mg/kg respectively, with mean concentration of copper 0.021mg/kg and for Zinc 0.007 mg/kg. Both metal results were found to be under limit, so it could be considered as safe. All water samples results are included in the table 1.

Results of Soil Samples:

Soil Samples were collected from selected sites *i.e.* two from Magod, two from Gorwada, five from Kakdkuva, three from Saronda, two from Jespor and two from Anklas; total 17 surface soil samples were collected. All soil samples were examined for metals *viz.* Lead, Cadmium, Zinc, Nickel, Cobalt, Cadmium and Mercury. **In all 17 soil samples copper and cobalt were detected to be beyond permissible limits**, while Zn and Ni were in the range of permissible limits. Copper detected between the range of 360880- 120.802mg/kg with mean concentration was 81.777mg/kg. In case of cobalt, higher cobalt level shows acidic soil (Krishna & Govil, 2007), and was detected in 10 samples out of 17 soil

samples between the range of 28.887-34.741mg/kg with mean concentration 20.887mg/kg. Zinc was detected in all 17 soil samples between the range of 35.569-92.132mg/kg with mean concentration 68.966mg/kg. Cadmium was detected in 7 samples out of 17 soil samples between the range of 0.088-0.198mg/kg with mean concentration 0.062mg/kg. Mercury was detected in 10 samples out of 17 soil samples between the range of 0.125-0.988mg/kg with mean concentration 0.321mg/kg. Lead was not detected in any of 17 soil samples. All soil sample with results are shown in table 2 and figure 2.

Results of Crops/Plants:

In case of vegetables, approximately 44 samples were tested for heavy metals *Viz* Pb, Cu, Cd, Zn, Co, Ni, Hg. Among all the 44 vegetable samples, Pb was not detected in any, Cu was detected in all 44 samples, however, **25 samples were beyond permissible limits**. The range was between 8.889-52.94mg/kg with mean concentration was 30.976 mg/kg. Cadmium was detected in 35 vegetable samples out of 44 samples, and was present under permissible limit. The range between 0.001-0.668mg/kg with mean concentration 0.117mg/kg. Zinc was detected in all 44 samples; out of which **10 samples were beyond permissible limits**. The values were between 0.125-62.751mg/kg with mean concentration was 34.599mg/kg. Cobalt was detected in 19 samples out of 44 samples and in all cobalt was found to be under limit. The values were between 0.189-0.601mg/kg with mean concentration was 0.153mg/kg. Nickel was detected in 37 samples out of 44 samples where **19 samples showed Nickel beyond permissible limits**. The range was between 0.069-2.35mg/kg with mean concentration was 0.931mg/kg. Mercury was detected in 22 samples out of 44 samples and **06 samples showed mercury beyond permissible limits**. The range was between 0.057-26.752mg/kg with mean concentration 1.868 mg/kg. All vegetable samples with detected Concentrations are shown in the Table 3 and figure 3.

Discussion:

The present research suggest that the irrigation water was safe. It was found safe in Varanasi too (Sharma et al, 2006), while Cd, Ni, Pb were found to be significantly high in water samples in Kutch, Gujarat (Patel et al, 2019). In concurrence with this work the research carried out all over the world on soil, showed higher values of different metals including copper and cobalt like current research. Cobalt was found on higher side in soil samples from industrial areas of Surat (Krishna & Govil, 2007), hazardous arsenic and cadmium metal were found to be high in soil samples around the vicinity of Brick Kiln in Bangladesh (Proshad et al, 2017). Cadmium metal values were found highest in soyabean plant in Dunhua Sewage Irrigation areas of China (Liang et al, 2011). While in crop's, metal accumulation was found for Zn higher than acceptable limits in plants like cabbage, brinjal, palak and Amaranthus in Varanasi (Sharma et al, 2006). Similar research a done for Zn in some leguminous plants, peas showed highest concentration 71.77mg/kg and Hg in some vegetables in Saudi Arabia (Ali et al, 2012). Cu in Mango, tomato, brinjal and Zn in some crops, found higher than acceptable limits. (Patel & Das, 2015). Copper, Zinc and lead were found to be higher than limits in shoots of different plants than roots in Islamabad, Pakistan (Malik et al, 2010). High levels of chromium, cadmium and lead were found beyond maximum permissible limit in sorghum plant in Punjab (Bhatti et al, 2015).

Bioaccumulation of Metals in Plants:

Bioaccumulation simply means accumulation of metals in plants which they are absorbing through the soil content. Different plants have different absorption quality; hence Bioaccumulation factors differ. Accumulation is divided in four scales (Pachura et al, 2015) that is <0.01 indicates no accumulation,

0.01-0.1 low accumulation, 0.1-1 medium accumulation and >1 is high accumulation. On the basis of this scale, 06 crops have high Copper BAF- in washed chili(Kakadkuva), washed cabbage(Gundlav), washed brinjal(Gundlav), unwashed cabbage(Gundlav), unwashed brinjal(Gundlav), unwashed brinjal(Kakadkuva) in Figure:4, 06 crops have high Cadmium BAF- washed spinah (jesppor),washed brinjal(Gundlav), unwashed brinjal(Kakadkuva), washed brinjal (Kakadkuva), washed Cabage(Gundlav), unwashed brinjal(Gundlav) in Figure:5, 07 crops have high Zinc BAF- washed chili(Kakadkuva), Washed kothmir(Jespor), washed brinjal(Kakadkuva), washed cabbage(Gundlav), washed brinjal(Gundlav), unwashed brinjal(Gundlav), unwashed cabbage(Gundlav) in Figure:7, 06 crops have high Nickel BAF- washed brinjal(Kakadkuva), washed okara(Kakadkuva-2 samples), washed mango(Gundlav), unwashed brinjal(Kakadkuva),unwashed mango (Gundlav) in Figure:8, 03 crops have high Mercury BAF -washed chili (Jespor), washed cabbage (Sarontha),washed tomato(Magod) in Figure:9 while cobalt have no accumulation and low accumulation in Figure:6.

CONCLUSION:

The water samples were collected from the bore wells. The water samples do match the national standards and prove that the deep lying aquifers are free of contamination and therefore the water is safe for irrigation (source borewells) throughout the area under study. Whereas the surface soil samples are by and large contaminated with heavy metals, at this point of time one cannot suggest the source of origin of metal contamination as the sum amount of the metal absorbed by the plants from soil, leading to high range of metal accumulation in the vegetables. The study also shows that washing procedure has little to no effect on heavy metal concentration in plants as they incorporated metals via uptake from soil in different concentrations and accumulation tendencies. High levels of Copper and Cobalt concentration were found in the soil samples, may indicate geological process rather than any anthropogenic activity. However, copper and mercury levels in crops were exceeded permissible limits defined by WHO guideline and FASSI guideline. From the research study, plants under higher accumulation factor indicates, the plants have absorbed and accumulated significant amount of these metals, making them potentially unsafe for human consumption. However, this study opens up a new vista of importance of creating a base line data for the whole industrial belt of state of Gujarat. This will provide scientific database to monitor the soil and water quality of the area.

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Table 1. Results of water from selected sites

Sample Name	Site	Type of sample	Pb MPL-0.01	Co* MPL-0.05-1.5	Cu MPL-0.05	Cd MPL-0.003	Ni MPL-0.02	Zn MPL-5	Hg MPL-0.001
Sample A	Saronda	Bore well	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	0.003	ND
Sample B	Kakdkuva	Bore well	ND	ND	0.021	ND	ND	ND	ND
Sample C	Jespore	Bore well	ND	ND	0.002	ND	ND	0.007	ND
Sample D	Anklas	Bore well	ND	ND	0.001	ND	ND	ND	ND

Note: All results are in mg/kg (milligram/kilogram)

MPL-Maximum permissible limit based on Indian standard *Denote WHO guideline

ND- Not Detected

Table 2. Results of Soil from selected sites

Sample Name	Selected Site	Pb* MPL 250-500	Cu MPL-30	Cd* MPL-3-6	Zn MPL-200	Co MPL-17	Ni MPL-80	Hg** MPL-0.5
Sample-A	Magod	ND	120.802	ND	92.132	28.853	54.459	ND
Sample-B		ND	138.575	ND	100.939	33.798	60.507	0.033
Sample-C	Gorwada	ND	37.516	0.088	57.611	ND	0.802	0.308
Sample-D	Ovada	ND	37.046	0.12	35.805	ND	ND	0.562
Sample-E		ND	117.599	ND	68.863	25.647	64.746	ND
Sample-F	Kakadkuva	ND	45.742	0.197	42.711	ND	1.309	0.559
Sample-G	Kakadkuva	ND	51.588	0.128	40.649	ND	0.952	ND
Sample-H		ND	169.946	ND	144.94	33.663	42.839	ND
Sample-I		ND	37.055	0.198	39.826	ND	ND	0.919
Sample-J		ND	51.76	0.173	44.312	ND	0.797	0.988
Sample-K	Saronda	ND	95.027	ND	83.496	34.066	63.016	0.125
Sample-L		ND	93.328	ND	76.845	34.741	60.396	ND
Sample-M		ND	63.107	ND	61.476	21.093	30.179	ND
Sample-N	Jespor	ND	129.318	ND	94.293	33.772	70.038	0.967
Sample-O		ND	36.88	0.151	35.569	ND	ND	0.467
Sample-P	Anklas	ND	87.23	ND	81.721	55.673	41.785	ND
Sample-Q		ND	77.688	ND	71.242	20.011	37.995	0.539

Note: All results are in mg/kg (milligram per kilogram)

MPL-Maximum permissible limit based on WHO guideline (WHO, 1996)

*Indian standard guideline, **European unit, ND- Not Detected

Table 3. Results of Plant/Crop from selected sites

Sr. No.	Sample Name	Selected Site	Pb MPL- 2.5	Cu MPL- 30	Cd MPL- 1.5	Zn MPL- 50	Co* MPL- 50	Ni MPL- 1.5	Hg** MPL- 1.0
1.	Washed cabbage	Saronda	ND	39.244	0.154	55.621	ND	0.069	0.161
2.	Unwashed cabbage	Saronda	ND	41.928	0.156	50.085	ND	ND	0.652
3.	Washed cauliflower	Ovada	ND	36.824	0.124	53.574	ND	0.736	0.226
4.	Unwashed cauliflower	Ovada	ND	46.42	0.105	46.59	ND	0.581	17.554
5.	Washed cabbage	Ovada	ND	37.994	0.153	62.751	ND	0.858	0.206
6.	Unwashed cabbage	Ovada	ND	51.751	0.096	41.303	ND	0.889	ND
7.	Unwashed chili	Gorwada	ND	46.863	0.142	45.375	ND	0.749	17.701
8.	Washed chilli	Gorwada	ND	36.502	0.187	40.078	ND	ND	1.019
9.	Unwashed brinjal	Ovada	ND	44.907	0.129	42.294	ND	1.257	0.163
10.	Washed brinjal	Ovada	ND	47.824	0.17	43.476	ND	1.509	0.532
11.	Washed chili	Kakadkuva	ND	37.862	0.114	54.19	ND	0.205	0.057
12.	Unwashed chili	Kakadkuva	ND	32.429	ND	30.687	ND	0.551	ND
13.	Unwashed brinjal	Magod	ND	40.825	0.106	55.862	ND	0.393	0.350
14.	Washed brinjal	Magod	ND	38.55	0.088	58.05	ND	0.983	0.157
15.	Washed tomato	Magod	ND	38.701	0.11	36.176	ND	ND	0.577
16.	Unwashed tomato	Magod	ND	38.712	0.108	40.719	ND	1.954	26.752
17.	Washed brinjal	Owada	ND	38.427	0.178	54.043	ND	0.913	0.261

18.	Unwashed brinjal	Owada	ND	52.413	0.194	44.282	ND	1.015	0.923
19.	Washed chili	Jespor	ND	37.815	0.146	39.847	ND	ND	1.099
20.	Unwashed tomato	Kakadkuva	ND	43.516	0.098	50.228	ND	ND	0.616
21.	Washed tomato	Kakadkuva	ND	38.562	0.079	0.125	ND	ND	0.789
22.	Unwashed brinjal	Saronda	ND	33.388	0.07	30.301	ND	ND	0.751
23.	Washed brinjal	Saronda	ND	30.326	0.075	33.99	ND	0.66	ND
24.	Unwashed brinjal	Magod dungari	ND	52.94	0.088	41.008	ND	1.01	0.096
25.	Unwashed tomato	Magod dungari	ND	39.835	0.172	41.533	ND	0.88	11.534
26.	Unwashed Mango	Ovada	ND	16.712	0.001	53.086	0.211	0.882	ND
27.	Washed Mango	Ovada	ND	19.647	0.027	16.797	0.189	1.247	ND
28.	Washed Mango	Jespor	ND	21.023	0.03	14.699	0.193	1.052	ND
29.	Unwashed Okra	Anklas	ND	23.317	0.196	38.001	0.295	1.664	ND
30.	Washed Okra	Anklas	ND	20.091	0.247	35.691	0.312	1.644	ND
31.	Unwashed Chiku	Owada	ND	12.474	0.015	11.698	0.196	1.678	ND
32.	Washed Chiku	Owada	ND	18.742	ND	11.202	0.348	0.946	ND
33.	Washed Chiku	Jespor	ND	15.077	ND	7.599	0.2	1.634	ND
34.	Washed Spinach	Owada	ND	21.757	0.289	24.769	0.544	1.662	ND
35.	Unwashed Okra	Kakadkuva	ND	11.739	0.099	16.659	0.201	0.861	ND
36.	Washed Okra	Kakadkuva	ND	22.356	0.037	23.813	0.482	1.656	ND
37.	Washed Okra	Kakadkuva	ND	17.991	0.085	26.361	0.601	1.329	ND
38.	Unwashed Mango	Magod	ND	20.215	0.022	47.065	0.281	0.984	ND

39.	Washed Mango	Magod	ND	18.223	0.205	22.982	0.516	1.19	ND
40.	Washed Spinach	Jespor	ND	25.093	0.668	33.742	0.539	1.227	ND
41.	Washed Tomato	Anklas	ND	14.593	ND	9.315	0.412	1.887	ND
42.	Washed Chili	Anklas	ND	17.788	0.147	18.672	0.542	2.325	ND
43.	Washed Chiku	Saronda	ND	12.667	ND	10.393	0.387	1.077	ND
44.	Unwashed Chiku	Saronda	ND	8.889	0.049	7.631	0.293	0.795	ND

Note: All results are in mg/kg (milligram per kilogram)

MPL-Maximum permissible limit based on Indian standard

*Denote WHO/FAO **Denote FSSAI guideline

Figure: 1 An outline map showing the area under study

Figure: 2 Chart shows Soil concentration with permissible limit mg/kg

Figure: 3 Chart shows vegetable concentration with metal permissible limit mg/kg

Figure: 4 Bioaccumulating Factor of Copper

Figure: 5 Bioaccumulating Factor of Cadmium

Figure: 6 Bioaccumulation Factor of Cobalt

Figure: 7 Bioaccumulation Factor of Zinc

Figure: 8 Bioaccumulation factor of Nickel

Figure: 9 Bioaccumulating Factor of Mercury